

Integration of ICT and Nai Talim in Education

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Abstract— ICT is the Information, Communication and Technology. Information is the data which is to be presented. Communication is the exchange of that information. Technology is the medium through which this exchange of information happens. Therefore, ICT is the medium of using technology for the exchange of information. Nai talim is the principle which highlights the importance of work education. It could be called as one of the type of the education that could be imparted through work, i.e. various kinds of work which are productive and related to handicraft. This paper has tried to integrate ICT and principles of Nai Talim in Education. For the integration of these in the education system, this could be seen through three perspectives in the teaching learning process as:

- ICT in Nai Talim principles
- Nai Talim principles in ICT
- Amalgamation.

Keywords— ICT, Nai Talim, Education.

I. INFORMATION COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY

ICT is the Information, Communication and Technology. Information is the data which is to be presented. Communication is the exchange of that information. Technology is the medium through which this exchange of information happens. Therefore, ICT is the medium of using technology for the exchange of information. This exchange could be in any field or area of expertise. In education, this exchange of the information is the transaction or specifically teaching learning process. To make this teaching learning process relevant, interesting and of improved quality, we use ICT as a tool to transact with the students. Therefore, ICT in education helps in a number of ways in transacting the information and providing knowledge to the students:

- Using ICT in education removes linguistic barrier in learning. Many languages could be used to transact the information and provide knowledge.
- Its use makes the teaching learning process interesting so as to enhance the retention power of the students.
- Use of ICT leads to better understanding of the concepts clarifying all the doubts and confusions.
- Spatial learning is enhanced through the use of ICT in education. Students get the almost real view of the content. They could visualize and understand the concept effectively.
- Improves the skills of teachers, students as well as of parents.
- ICT provides up to date information to the students.
- ICT provides focused learning environment.
- It is flexible in learning and providing the learning environment.

- ICT makes the student active learner. Students actively participate in the process and learn.
- ICT makes the learner independent in learning.
- It enables the content to be interactive and it makes the learning relevant.
- It leads to the learning at the learners' own pace. Through ICT, a learner could move as per the need. The pace of learning through ICT is as per the pace of learning of the learner.

II. NAI TALIM

“The principal idea is to instruct the whole education of the body, mind and soul through the handicraft that is taught to the children.” -MAHATMA GANDHI

Nai talim is the principle which highlights the importance of work education. It could be called as one of the type of the education that could be imparted through work, i.e. various kinds of work which are productive and related to handicraft. The various components of Nai Talim could be described as follows:

- 3H (Head, Heart and Hands): Nai Talim involves the inculcation of 3Hs i.e. Head, which relates to involvement of mind in the process of learning. Heart i.e. it relates to sensitive aspect of education. It means that whatever is learned, it is learned through heart. Hands i.e. active participation of the students where they actually perform the activities by themselves.
- Use of mother tongue: Nai Talim emphasizes the use of mother tongue as the instructional language. It provides the linkages between the content and the learner which leads to better understanding.
- Craft centered: Nai Talim emphasizes the use of craft in the teaching learning process. The learning is made relevant and interesting through the use of craft.
- Dignity of labour: Nai Talim focuses put emphasis on the dignity of labour. It should be practiced by the students.
- Self-reliance: This is one of the important component of the Nai Talim wherein focus is to enable students to be self reliant. The focus is on teaching which would make the students self reliant.

“I hold that the highest development of the mind and the soul is possible under such a system of education. Only every handicraft has to be taught not merely mechanically as is done today, but scientifically i.e. the child should know the why and wherefore of every process....I have myself taught sandal-making and even spinning on these lines with good results. This method does not exclude knowledge of history and geography. But I find that this is best taught by transmitting

such general information By word of mouth. One imparts ten times as much in this manner as by reading and writing. The signs of the alphabet may be taught later...Of course, the pupil learns mathematics through his handicraft.

I attach the greatest importance to primary education, which according to my conception should be equal to the present matriculation less English...."Harijan of the 31st July 1937 ""

After considering both these principles, if one wants to have a teaching learning process which has the maximum input and also which will result in maximum outcome through better learning of the students, it's a need to integrate these two. If we would integrate these two, we will get the benefit of both. This paper has tried to integrate ICT and principles of Nai Talim in Education. For the integration of these in the education system, this could be seen through three perspectives in the teaching learning process as:

- ICT in Nai Talim principles
- Nai Talim principles in ICT
- Amalgamation

❖ *ICT in Nai Talim principles:*

In this perspective, we try to include ICT in the principles of Nai Talim. It means we are adopting the principles of Nai Talim and we try to include ICT as an aid. In this part, we use ICT as a tool to teach various concepts when we are actually dealing with those concepts with the Nai Talim principles. For example, in dealing with water conservation as an example, we are teaching this concept by actually taking up the students to the areas showing how conservation is done. After the visit, for the conclusion, we could show some videos related to this which would sensitize the students regarding water conservation.

❖ *Nai Talim principles in ICT:*

For this perspective, we try to include Nai Talim principles in the teaching of ICT. When we are teaching the ICT using various tools and techniques, we could include those practices which include the principles of Nai Talim like including Head, Heart and Hands. This knowledge could be provided in mother tongue and when this will focus on the self-reliance principle. Learning ICT through the use of Head, Heart and Hands, using mother tongue and being self-reliant through this comes under this category.

❖ *Amalgamation:*

In this portion, we try to amalgamate the two. For this we integrate both the principles as per the need. When we are

dealing with any concept, as per the need and requirement of the topic we could include principles of both. For example:

- ✓ In the subject science, for the teaching of flora, we could take students to explore different types of flora additionally showing them the videos related to it.
- ✓ In the subject social sciences, local culture could be told to the students by actually making them experience the culture whereas global culture could be shown through the use of various tools like presentations, internet, related videos, etc.
- ✓ In the teaching of language subjects, various audios could be used to enhance the vocabulary and pronunciation patterns.

III. CONCLUSION

To conclude the paper, we could say that to get the maximum outcome of the teaching learning process, it is very much needed to understand the context and deal with the concept accordingly. Teaching method is one of the important elements of the teaching learning process which could motivate or demotivate the students for learning. So, to make the learning interesting, creative as well as relevant it is very much needed to adopt the method which is as per the requirement and which provides maximum input whether it is ICT or Nai Talim principles or amalgamation of both. Every perspective has its own characteristics and by amalgamating these, we could get the benefits of both and could result in a better understanding among students.

REFERENCES

- [1] Benefits of ICT in learning and education(April, 2017) retrieved from <https://yourstory.com/mystory/8b5663d9bf-benefits-of-ict-in-learning-and-education>
- [2] Blurton, C.; "New Directions of ICT-Use in Education", <http://www.unesco.org/education/educprog/lwfi/dl/edict.pdf>; UNESCO World Communication and Information Report,1999
- [3] Introduction To Wardha Scheme Of Basic Education-1937, retrieved from <http://www.kkhsou.in/main/education/wardha.html>
- [4] <http://www.gandhiashramsevagram.org/village-swaraj/nai-talim.php#>
- [5] Jain M., Shikshantar Andolan and Swaraj University manish@swaraj.org, <http://shikshantar.org/articles/thoughts-resurrecting-nai-talim>
- [6] Mohanty Rashmi Ranjan, ICT Advantages & Disadvantages(February, 2011), Introduction to ICT, retrieved from <http://ict-adv-disadv.blogspot.com/>
- [7] Motwani Sachin, (October, 2013) retrieved from <https://www.slideshare.net/sachinmotwani526/ppt-on-nai-talim>
- [8] The story of nai talim, Fifty years of education at sevagram, India, (1937-1987) Retrieved from http://home.iitk.ac.in/~amman/soc748/sykes_story_of_nai_talim.html